

A Comparative Study of Black Feminism and Indian Feminism in Wole Soyinka's "The Lion and The Jewel" and Manju Kapur's "Difficult Daughters"

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Abstract

The word "comparative" is derived from Latin term "comparatives" generally speaking comparison is the common intense of humans experience. This common intense of human experience reveals itself in literary response and authentic appreciation. Comparative literature is the study of literature beyond the confines of one particular country and it's the study of the relationship between literature on one hand and other areas of knowledge and belief such as arts, philosophy, history, social science, science's and religion etc.

In India, the late Buddha Deva Bose first introduced it at Jadavapur University .And later it was introduced in 'The center Institute of English and Foreign Languages' , Hyderabad and in 'Madurai Kamaraj University' in South India. Similiarity and Dissimilarity are weighed interms of Systematically organized ,Scientifically arranged and Intelctually convencing way in order to validate the comparison.

" Comparative literature is laboratory or workshop of literary studies Comparative literature is not only has accommulsion of primary works But as the languages, culture, histories, tradition, theories, and practices With which thoughts works come '.

Roland Greene

Feminist criticism is one of the approaches in literary criticism. It examines the ways and means by which literature has been shaped according to the issues of gender. It supports the belief that women are not inferior to men and they should have the same rights and opportunities as men get. as a woman's movements it has got its inspiration from two earlier documents of feminist theory. one is simone de beauvoir's book "the second sex" and the other is kate millet's "sexual politics".

Both the works, Wole Soyinka's "The Lion and the Jewel" and Manju Kapur's "Difficult Daughters" examines the custom and rules made for women. Wole Soyinka has been a great contributor to the growth of African Literature in and outside Africa along with

Chinua Achebe. Wole Soyinka is a prolific Nigeria born dramatist won noble prize for literature and he was awarded a "Rockefeller Bursary". His works are rich in tradition and reveal the influence of colonizers on its colonies. As a dramatist Soyinka has been influenced by the Irish writer J.M. Synge.

An Indian writer Manju Kapur was born in Amritsar. Her first novel *Difficult Daughters* won the Commonwealth writer's prize in the year of 1999. And recognized as the best first book in Europe and Asia. Her novel 'The Immigrant' has been nominated for the DSC prize for South Asia Literature.

The play "The Lion and the Jewel" deals with traditional values like Bride Price and the place of women. The same in the "Difficult Daughters" the novel deeply explains the culture and tradition made for women's. We can compare the Sidi character in "The Lion and The Jewel" with Virmati character in "Difficult Daughters". Because both the characters Sidi and Virmati oppose the tradition and culture followed by the society. And these two characters expose the feminist concept through their life but at the end of the story both Sidi and Virmati failed in their aim.

The role of women in the society portrayed in the play 'The Lion and The Jewel' is close to the tradition of our country in some ways. Marriage is a social custom that mostly revolves around the idea of child bearing in most of the societies round the world. In case of Nigeria, it's not a different case. Lakunle, an ardent follower of western values, somehow challenges the custom. He says that he does not seek wife "to Fetch and Carry, to Cook, to Scrub, to Bring forth Children by the Gross...." But Sidi was not convinced by his adamant ideas and utters fearfully "Heaven Forgive You" to save him from the wrath of Gods. The society is still far away from Modern Industrialization and women are engaged in traditional household activities. Like "The Lion and The Jewel", the novel "Difficult Daughters" also examines the real motive of marriage. Expect Virmati and Shakuntala the other women in the novel *Lajwanthi*, *Kasturi*, *Kishori Devi*, *Ganga* conform to Patriarchal system of family. They take pride in being submissive to men. According to them Domesticity, Marriage and Child bearing are the duties of women. *Kasturi* was brought up upon the tradition that marriage is the ultimate destiny of a girl and she has to please her in laws. According to her women without her own home and family is a woman without moorings. She feels grateful to her mother for those long hours she spent in the kitchen in cooking. When Virmati wants to go to Lahore to pursue higher studies she says,

*'when I was your age, girls only left their house
When they married. And beyond a certain age'*.

The novel is like a critical analysis of the patriarchal modes of thinking. It aims at the domination of male and the subordination of the female. The pattern of society teaches women to internalize the concept of subordination. But what about herself realization? Tradition presents the systematic attempts to silence the female, culture demands from her to be feminine. All through the novel, Manju Kapur strongly emphasizes the plea that the worldly forces are not responsible for the protagonist to fall deep into melancholic void, but her own inner desires. Traditionally, the Indian woman is represented as priceless wooden creature. She is subjected to male domination such as set up of society, this hostile to women's endeavor. The same in the Soyinka's play "The Lion and The Jewel" exposed the male domination through the character of Bale Baroka.

Both these characters Sidi and Virmati lost their life by the patriarchy of men. In the play "The Lion and the Jewel" the character Bale Baroka portrays himself as a strictly traditional. As a Yoruban ruler he is determined to keep his village the same way. He stops the western civilization from spreading to his village the public works attempt to build a railway in Lujinle, but Baroka is against progress. They send in workers and surveyors to tear down jungles in order to run a railway

through village. When Baroka learns of this, he brines off the surveyor. Sidi's photos appeared in glossary magazine under the title 'Beauty beyond the Dreams of Goodness'. It shows the progress of women in the society .Baroka set his eyes on Sidi.He knows how to use her ego against her.He knows that if he can seduce Sidi,she will not have a choice in marrying him.ThoughBaroka is sixty two years old,he wins the hand of Sidi at last.Baroka already had many wives even his wife Sadiku helped Bale Baroka to win Sidi.

Like Bale Baroka , the character of Harish in Difficult Daughters was already married and had two children. Harish is a renowned professor from oxford. In the entire college his classroom is the most crowded one .He brings the subject alive Virmati is fascinated and sees sophistication in Harish life. His ability to understand English literature, particularly poetry ,his liking for tea in delicate China cups and his gramophone charm Virmati. His wife is illiterate and he does not consider her as his soul mate. The strong personality of Virmati draws him closer to her . He develops illicit love for Virmati. He exploits her with his words soaked in love. As virmati is thirsting for love, by repeated overtures he forces his mind into her heart and wins over her. She gets caught in the strong passion towards him and the strength of her personality dissolves. When she learns that the professor wife is pregnant, she is puzzled how the professor has his love for her on the one hand and has been close with his wife on the other hand .She loses hope and goes to Lahore for further studies. She realizes the male chauvinistic attitude of the professor and tells him on his face ,

*'you think you can do what you like so long as
You go on saying you love''.*

Illicit relationship with Virmati results in her unwed pregnancy and painful termination .Virmati aborts the child and feels emptiness. When she proposes her marriage with him he fears that it will spoil his reputation and his family's name and refuses to marry her. She leaves him and becomes the headmistress of a girl's school in the hill station of Sirmaur.

But he still visits her secretly and exploits her sexually. She falls as a victim to his sexual oppression. He sends her to study philosophy so that she gets away from the suffocating atmosphere in his house. Virmati resolves not to return to him but as for any woman at that time marriage was the only validation of femininity and she continues to writing letter to him. Harish takes advantages of this expectation of Virmati. He lacks will power and courage to marry Virmati because he does not want to displace his first wife. It is only after five years he agrees to marry Virmati after a lot of persuasion by his friend. But this marriage proves disastrous. Though virmati becomes the legally wedded second wife of Harish .She is ostracized by her family and alienated from her husband family. It is only because of Harish , Virmati the protagonist has to live hidden from society and her beloved ones.

Bale Baroka in Soyinka's 'The Lion and The Jewel' and Harish in Kapur's 'Difficult Daughters' are the best example for male domination These character did not think about the feelings of women , instead they look only the sexual pleasure in women.

At the beginning of the play , Sidi likes the modern life for example : She feels much proud of herself for appear her photos in magazine but at the end she failed to won Baroka. She was trapped in Baroka plan. Like Sidi , Virmati in difficult daughters" loosed herself in the words of Harish. Like Sidi ,Virmati also plans to move in modern way. For example: She rejects the marriage, attempts suicide and bears imprisonment. She aspires to be like her cousin Sakunthala who tastes independence. She desires to lead life according to her priorities. To liberate herself she looks to education and joins Lahore college. She clears her FA and joins A.S.college , 'the bastion of male learning' . But after meet Harish, situation was totally changed,

*'when Harish is here, I stop thinking of others.....
when he is not here, all I do is to wait for him to come' [144].*

The educational opportunities are available to Virmati but she cannot take the proper advantage of it. As a daughter according to her mom she has betrayed and solvent of them.

Wole Soyinka's 'The Lion and The Jewel' is a celebration of tradition and its richness. Africans are deep rooted in their tradition. Women are suppressed by the name of Custom and Tradition. The in same in Kapur's Difficult Daughters with her Dichotomies, Spousaltensions ,and Domestic traumas under takes the quest for female identity. Manju Kapur has been a significantly sensational women artist. The novelist as a woman is shaped by the same environment and is a part of distinction of patriarchy. It is a confrontation of the female protagonist with patriarchal oppressive environment that adds more sharpness to the vision of the novelist.

References

1. Soyinka, Wole, 'The Lion and The Jewel'.
2. 'Wole Soyinka', 'Orient Black Swan'.
3. Brains, Paul 'wole Soyinka study Guide'.
4. Tubman , Howard 'A Nigerian looks at progress' 'The New york Times'.
5. Kapur, Manju. Difficult Daughters, London: Faber and Faber Ltd ,1999.